

A Hierarchical Deep Learning Framework for Rapid Eye Movement Behavior Disorder Detection

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Abstract—Rapid Eye Movement (REM) Behavior Disorder (RBD) is a parasomnia strongly associated with future neurodegenerative diseases, yet its diagnosis depends on labor-intensive polysomnography (PSG) analysis and analytical indices such as the REM Atonia Index (RAI). Automated detection is challenging due to the temporal sparsity and variability of RBD-related events.

This work presents SOMNUS-RBD, a hierarchical deep learning framework for patient-level RBD prediction from REM sleep PSG. REM segments are encoded into embeddings, then processed with channel-level attention pooling and temporal Log-SumExp aggregation to capture sparse pathological activations. Five data configurations were evaluated on a 49-patient cohort using 10-repeated 5-fold cross-validation: (1) chin electromyography (EMG) embeddings alone, (2) multichannel EMG with independent per-channel embeddings, (3) multichannel EMG with joint multi-channel embeddings, (4) multimodal EMG, electroencephalography (EEG) and electrooculography (EOG) with independent per-channel embeddings, and (5) multimodal EMG, EEG, and EOG with unified per-modality embeddings.

Using only chin EMG, the proposed framework showed improvements compared to the analytical baseline (RAI), as accuracy increased from 0.735 to 0.786 and recall from 0.577 to 0.781, while maintaining competitive precision and AUC. Independent multichannel EMG achieved the best performance with an AUC of 0.832 and a recall of 0.827. In contrast, grouping channels prior to embedding extraction reduced discriminative performance. Attention weights highlighted EMG as the dominant modality compared to EEG and EOG, and temporal importance scores aligned with physiologically meaningful segments of loss of atonia. These findings suggest that SOMNUS-RBD surpasses traditional analytical indices while providing intrinsic channel- and timestep-relevant measures for RBD detection.

Index Terms—Clinical Decision Support, Deep Learning, Foundation Models, Polysomnography, REM Behavior Disorder.

I. INTRODUCTION

Rapid Eye Movement (REM) Behavior Disorder (RBD) is a parasomnia characterized by the loss of muscle atonia and the enactment of dreams during REM sleep. Its diagnosis is clinically significant, as RBD has been correlated with future

neurodegenerative disorders, often preceding their clinical onset by several years, including Parkinson’s Disease (PD) and Dementia with Lewy Bodies (DLB) [1], which emphasizes the need for early detection and timely clinical intervention. A large systematic review and meta-analysis [2] reported an estimated conversion risk of approximately 33% within five years of diagnosis, increasing to over 80% after about ten years and exceeding 90% with longer follow-up, with PD accounting for roughly 40% to 45% of conversions and DLB for approximately 25%. Despite its clinical relevance, RBD remains underdiagnosed as a definitive diagnosis relies on clinical and technical expertise that is not universally available in routine healthcare practice [3].

Manual analysis of polysomnography (PSG) recordings for RBD prediction imposes a substantial burden on sleep technicians, as they must review several hours of data to identify rare and subtle episodes of REM sleep without atonia (RSWA) or abnormal behaviors. The diagnostic process requires an overnight recording during which only a fraction of total sleep time, typically 20% to 25% in healthy adults, is spent in REM sleep [4]. As a result, clinically relevant events are temporally sparse, and abnormal behaviors may occur only once or not at all during a given night, particularly in early or mild cases of RBD. Furthermore, RSWA and dream enactment behaviors are episodic and variable, increasing the risk of false negatives in single-night studies [5]. The post-acquisition workflow is equally demanding as trained sleep technologists and clinicians must annotate PSG activity and contextualize RBD events, which may also lead to inter-rater variability [6]. However, Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) have emerged as powerful solutions in computer-aided diagnostic systems, hence motivating their application to data-driven modeling of PSG recordings for RBD prediction.

This work presents SOMNUS-RBD, a novel DL framework for automated RBD prediction through PSG signals across REM episodes to estimate the probability of RBD diagnosis in a patient. In addition to generating patient-level predictions, the framework also produces timeline heatmaps designed to support clinical interpretation by facilitating the identification of RBD-related patterns. Moreover, this study explores the use of various electrophysiologic signals for RBD diagnosis, including electroencephalography (EEG) and electrooculography (EOG), in addition to standard electromyography (EMG).

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews related work on computational approaches for

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RBD detection. Section III describes the dataset, the RAI baseline, the proposed hierarchical DL framework, and the experimental setup. Section IV presents and discusses the quantitative results, and analyzes PSG channel and temporal importance weights. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and outlines future research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

Initial studies in RBD detection using computational methods predominantly adopted analytical approaches aimed at quantifying motor activity during sleep and summarizing it through predefined indices. For instance, Burns et al. [7] proposed an automated metric based on EMG variance during REM sleep, computed relative to subject-specific non-REM baselines, to replicate and accelerate established visual scoring procedures for RBD assessment. Similarly, Ferri et al. [8] introduced REM Atonia Index (RAI), a rule-based measure quantifying the proportion of low-amplitude submental EMG activity across REM mini-epochs, and demonstrated its ability to discriminate between healthy controls, idiopathic RBD patients, and related neurological conditions.

Subsequent studies shifted toward ML-based approaches, employing information from multiple physiological signals and feature-driven strategies. Kempfner et al. [9] introduced one of the earliest ML-based approaches to automated RBD identification as an outlier-detection problem using Support Vector Machine (SVM) models. Moreover, Cesari et al. [10] proposed an ML framework based on EEG and EOG signals, using Random Forest classifiers to identify RBD in PD patients and to predict progression from prodromal REM behavioral events. Additionally, Lee et al. [11] researched ML applied to diffusion tensor imaging, employing SVMs on handcrafted features and structural measures to distinguish idiopathic RBD patients from healthy controls.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

The dataset used in this study employs a proprietary cohort collected at Unidade de Saúde Local São João, including PSG recordings from 49 patients. For each subject, the dataset provides the full PSG signals, annotated sleep staging, and a binary diagnosis of RBD, where a positive diagnosis is labeled as 1 and a negative diagnosis as 0. The class distribution is balanced, with 23 patients ($\approx 47\%$) presenting a negative RBD diagnosis and 26 patients ($\approx 53\%$) a positive diagnosis.

The physiological signals analyzed in this work include five EMG channels positioned at the chin, upper limbs and lower limbs, five EEG channels corresponding to the central right (C4), frontal left (F3), frontal right (F4), occipital left (O1) and occipital right (O2) scalp locations, which were the only EEG derivations consistently available across all patients, and two EOG channels placed at the left outer canthus (LOC) and right outer canthus (ROC). All signals were acquired at a sampling frequency of 500 Hz. Fig. 1 displays a snippet of the chin EMG during a REM sleep episode from the dataset.

Fig. 1. Example of a chin EMG signal during a REM sleep episode.

B. RAI Baseline

The aforementioned RAI method from Ferri et al. [8] is a widely adopted quantitative marker in sleep medicine for assessing REM sleep muscle atonia, providing a robust baseline for this study. Firstly, the chin EMG signal is digitally band-pass filtered (10-100Hz) and notch filtered at 50Hz to attenuate line noise, then rectified to obtain absolute amplitude values. Next, each REM epoch is subdivided into 1-second windows. For every 1-second segment, the average amplitude of the rectified chin EMG is calculated, and a correction is applied by subtracting the minimum amplitude found within a moving 60-second window. This assumes the minimum value within that window approximates the local noise floor, enabling adaptive normalization across the night.

After preprocessing, each 1-second REM mini-epoch is classified according to its average amplitude. The RAI is defined as the ratio between the number of REM mini-epochs with average amplitude lower or equal than $1 \mu V$ and the total number of valid REM mini-epochs, excluding those with amplitudes between $1 \mu V$ and $2 \mu V$ to avoid ambiguity around the threshold. Additionally, identifying REM mini-epochs with average chin EMG amplitude lower or equal than $1 \mu V$ allows the construction of an atonia index map across REM periods of the PSG recording, which may support clinicians by excluding segments with RAI-confirmed muscle atonia during diagnostic review.

Empirically, $RAI < 0.8$ is strongly indicative of abnormal REM atonia [8]. Therefore, this threshold was applied to determine RBD status in this study's cohort, with patients classified as positive when $RAI < 0.8$ and negative otherwise.

C. RBD Detection Framework

The proposed RBD detection method comprises two main components: a pretrained foundation model trained on PSG data and a task-specific classification head. While it produces patient-level predictions, the framework is primarily intended as a diagnostic tool to assist early detection and prioritize cases for expert review.

Firstly, the framework employs SleepFM, a transformer-based foundation model from Thapa et al. [12] that was trained on more than 585,000 hours of PSG recordings from over 65,000 participants across multiple cohorts. Initially, all signals are resampled to 128Hz, fourth-order low-pass Butterworth filtered in zero-phase mode to prevent aliasing prior to downsampling, and subsequently normalized zero mean and unit variance. Afterwards, the signals are segmented into non-overlapping 5-second windows, which serve as the model's input tokens. Lastly, the foundation model was pretrained by

extracting 5-second embeddings for each modality across the entire night, while using a context-window of 5 minutes, and optimized using Leave-one-out Contrastive Learning. Furthermore, employing SleepFM also enables the use of any cohort’s PSG data.

In this work, SleepFM was used as a frozen feature extractor. After applying the same preprocessing pipeline, each EMG channel was independently passed through SleepFM to obtain a sequence of 128-dimensional embeddings, where each embedding represents a 5-second segment of signal activity. In addition, embeddings were extracted at the group level by jointly considering all available channels within each physiological group (EEG, EMG, and EOG). Lastly, since RBD-related behaviors are solely present during REM sleep, only the embeddings during REM episodes are considered. Therefore, each patient’s data is divided into REM episodes, as shown in Fig. 2.

Secondly, the downstream task classification head is optimized to output probability values regarding a positive diagnosis of RBD using the embeddings extracted from SleepFM for each patient. Due to the data structure of the REM episodes embedding sequences, the model works hierarchically on the data. Initially, at the signal channels level, a shallow Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) introduces task-specific adaptation of the pretrained embeddings, followed by attention pooling over the channels. Consequently, a bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) network processes each REM sequence independently to capture temporal dependencies within each sequence and to model signal activation patterns. Considering the sparse occurrence of RBD-related events during REM sleep, it is reasonable to employ OR-like activations when performing temporal pooling over the processed embedding sequences. Accordingly, LogSumExp is used as a smooth alternative

Fig. 2. Hierarchical structure of the input data used for RBD prediction. PSG signals are segmented into 5-second windows and encoded into fixed-length embeddings per channel. Embeddings are grouped by REM episodes, where each episode contains a temporal sequence of S representations with C channels. Multiple REM episodes are available per patient, forming a hierarchical organization.

to max pooling, enabling aggregation across each sequence while giving greater weight to embedding values of higher magnitude. Finally, each pooled representation passes through an MLP to regularize the GRU-derived features and capture episode-specific characteristics before episode-level average pooling. This yields a patient-level embedding, which is then passed through a single fully connected layer to produce the output logit. The overall hierarchical classification head architecture is framed in Fig. 3.

D. Channel and Temporal Importance Weights

The hierarchical structure of the proposed model enables the extraction of intrinsic importance weights at both the channel and REM episodes sequence levels. These quantities are directly obtained from the attention-based channel pooling and the LogSumExp temporal aggregation, without requiring any post-hoc explainability technique. These weights allow us to check which signal channels and temporal segments most strongly influenced the model’s decision.

1) *Channel Weights*: Regarding attention pooling, let $\mathbf{h}_{e,s,c} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ denote the embedding vector corresponding to a REM episode e , sequence index s and channel c after the first task-adaptation projection. For each episode e and sequence step s , attention scores are computed as in (1), where \mathbf{w} is a learnable parameter vector.

$$\alpha_{e,s,c} = \frac{\exp(\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{h}_{e,s,c})}{\sum_{c'} \exp(\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{h}_{e,s,c'})}. \quad (1)$$

The coefficients $\alpha_{e,c,s}$ therefore quantify the relative contribution of each channel at the sequence step s within episode e , where larger values indicate that the corresponding modality was assigned greater relevance by the model at that specific temporal location.

2) *Temporal Weights*: After channel pooling, each REM episode is processed by a GRU network, producing hidden representations $\mathbf{h}_{e,s} \in \mathbb{R}^H$ for timesteps $s = 1, \dots, S_e$. Temporal aggregation is performed using LogSumExp pooling (2), which can be interpreted as a smooth approximation to max pooling, as stated before.

$$\mathbf{h}_e = \log \sum_{s=1}^{S_e} \exp(\mathbf{h}_{e,s}) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3. Architecture of the proposed hierarchical classification head. Channel embeddings are adapted with an MLP and aggregated using channel attention pooling. Each REM episode’s representations are processed with a GRU and temporal LogSumExp pooling, followed by episode average pooling to obtain a patient-level embedding for final positive RBD diagnosis probability.

More importantly, it induces an implicit softmax distribution over the timesteps of the corresponding REM episode. The corresponding timestep importance weights $\tau_{e,s}$ are computed as stated in (3).

$$\tau_{e,s} = \frac{\exp(\mathbf{h}_{e,s})}{\sum_{s'} \exp(\mathbf{h}_{e,s'})} \quad (3)$$

The coefficients $\tau_{e,s}$ quantify the relative influence of each timestep s on the episode-level representation, as higher values indicate temporal segments with stronger activation and greater contribution to the pooled embedding.

E. Experimental Setup

For this study, RAI was adopted as the baseline method for performance comparison, establishing a clinically grounded benchmark against SOMNUS-RBD. To evaluate the framework’s performance, five distinct experimental scenarios were designed to assess both comparability with the baseline and the incremental contribution of additional physiological signals.

The first experiment uses exclusively the chin EMG channel data, which corresponds to the same signal employed by RAI, ensuring direct comparability and evaluating whether the proposed architecture can outperform the baseline when using identical input information. The second and third experiments employ additional EMG channels (chin, arms, and legs) to determine whether incorporating broader muscle activity improves RBD prediction and to evaluate the impact of representation strategy. Both use the same five-channel data, differing only in embedding extraction, where the second generates independent embeddings per channel, while the third produces a single unified embedding from jointly processed multi-channel EMG input. Lastly, the fourth and fifth experiments incorporate EMG, EEG, and EOG signals to evaluate whether additional physiological information improves RBD detection over EMG-only setups. Both use the same data, differing only in representation, as the fourth extracts embeddings per channel, whereas the fifth generates a single embedding per signal type.

All experiments were evaluated using 10-repeated 5-fold cross-validation to ensure robust performance estimates given the small dataset size. For each cross-validation repetition, the dataset was partitioned into 70% training, 10% validation, and 20% testing splits at the patient level. Performance was assessed on the collected predictions for the test sets using accuracy, recall (sensitivity), precision (specificity) and AUC.

All models and experimental scenarios were trained using the same hyperparameter configuration to ensure fairness across comparisons. The number of training epochs was set to 50, with a batch size of 1, and binary cross-entropy was employed as the loss function. Optimization was performed using the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of 5×10^{-5} and default PyTorch parameters. These hyperparameters were determined through empirical experimentation on preliminary runs and were kept fixed across all training phases and experimental conditions. Please note that the SleepFM weights remain frozen throughout training.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Quantitative Performance

Table I summarizes the results for the RAI baseline and the performance of SOMNUS-RBD under the four experimental configurations previously described. All metrics are reported with the mean and standard deviation obtained across the repeated cross-validation procedure.

Firstly, using only the chin EMG data, RAI achieves an accuracy of 0.735 and an AUC of 0.824, with the highest precision of 0.882 but very limited recall of 0.577. The standard deviation of all metrics is zero because RAI is deterministic. This behavior reflects a conservative behavior that produces relatively few false positives at the expense of missing a substantial number of true RBD cases. On the other hand, when SOMNUS-RBD is optimized and evaluated on the same chin EMG signal, it improves accuracy to 0.786 and increases recall substantially to 0.781, while maintaining competitive precision (0.810) and AUC (0.820). The substantial gain in recall/sensitivity suggests a more balanced decision boundary, and, from a clinical perspective, the increase in true positive rate is particularly relevant, as reducing false negatives is critical in RBD diagnosis. Overall, under identical input conditions, the learned approach demonstrates superior classification balance with equally predictive performance compared to the rule-based RAI method.

Next, extending the input to include all available EMG channels and processing them independently through the foundation model preserves the same accuracy (0.786) while further improving recall to 0.827 and achieving the highest AUC (0.832) among all experiments. Additionally, precision shows a slight decrease in performance, although it remains competitive at 0.785. The inclusion of limb EMG channels appears to provide information that is not fully captured by chin EMG alone. The slight increase in AUC indicates improved discriminative performance of the model, while the higher recall suggests that additional EMG channels capture RBD-related motor activity that may not be fully detected when relying solely on the chin channel, which is consistent with limb movements observed in RBD, such as punching and kicking during REM sleep. In contrast, when the same EMG channels are grouped prior to embedding extraction, performance degrades across all metrics, although recall remains remarkably superior (0.788) than RAI’s (0.577). Nonetheless, these results suggest that collapsing multiple EMG channels into a single grouped representation may dilute channel-specific patterns, limiting the model’s ability to exploit different muscle activity data.

Finally, the experiments employing EMG, EEG and EOG signals display the same performance trend observed when grouping EMG channels prior to the foundation model, solidifying the idea that this aggregation strategy may lead to a diluted representation of modality-specific patterns. In particular, the fifth framework configuration yields the lowest overall performance, with accuracy of 0.671, recall of 0.731, precision of 0.678 and AUC of 0.728. Nevertheless, both recall

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE METRICS OF THE RAI BASELINE AND THE PROPOSED SOMNUS-RBD FRAMEWORK UNDER FOUR EXPERIMENTS. RESULTS ARE REPORTED AS MEAN \pm STANDARD DEVIATION OVER 10-REPEATED 5-FOLD CROSS-VALIDATION.

Method	PSG Signals	Accuracy	Recall (Sensitivity)	Precision (Specificity)	AUC
RAI [8]	Chin EMG	0.735*	0.577*	0.882*	0.824*
SOMNUS-RBD (Ours)	Chin EMG	0.786 \pm 0.043	0.781 \pm 0.065	0.810 \pm 0.046	0.820 \pm 0.033
	Individual EMGs	0.786 \pm 0.043	0.827 \pm 0.071	0.785 \pm 0.053	0.832 \pm 0.034
	Grouped EMGs	0.710 \pm 0.032	0.788 \pm 0.084	0.703 \pm 0.022	0.776 \pm 0.027
	Individual EMGs + EEGs + EOGs	0.722 \pm 0.043	0.746 \pm 0.071	0.737 \pm 0.053	0.791 \pm 0.034
	Grouped EMGs + EEGs + EOGs	0.671 \pm 0.035	0.731 \pm 0.057	0.678 \pm 0.039	0.728 \pm 0.070

*Standard deviation of the metrics values were not computed for RAI due to its deterministic behavior.

values still surpass that of the RAI baseline, indicating that, despite the reduced discriminative capacity, the approaches remain more sensitive to RBD cases than the analytical index. Furthermore, within the present framework and dataset size, these results show that adding EEG and EOG does not enhance RBD prediction. This may be due to RBD-related abnormalities being primarily expressed in muscle activity during REM sleep, while EEG and EOG introduce additional variability without a strong discriminative contribution.

B. Modality Importance

The plots in Fig. 4, Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 represent the distribution of attention weights for each signal type of the second, fourth and fifth experiments of this study, respectively.

In the second experiment, the chin EMG exhibits the highest median attention weight among all channels, consistent with its established role in REM atonia assessment and with its use in the RAI methodology. Moreover, RBD-positive patients show a relative increase in attention to the chin EMG compared with RBD-negative patients, although this relationship is not observed for the remaining EMG channels. However, the attention distribution is not sharply peaked on a single channel. The weights are well-balanced within the 0.18-0.23 range across channels, indicating that the model integrates information across multiple EMG sources rather than collapsing into a single dominant signal.

Regarding the fourth experiment, the EMG channels show higher attention score medians compared to their EEG and EOG channel counterparts when these are embedded inde-

pendently through the foundation model. Similarly, when EMG, EEG, and EOG channels are embedded jointly per modality in the fifth configuration, the attention mechanism also assigns the highest median weight to EMG, followed by EEG, with EOG receiving the lowest weight overall. These results confirm that muscle activity remains the principal discriminative PSG signal for RBD detection, even when additional physiological signals are introduced. Though, EEG still receives a non-negligible portion of the total attention weight, meaning that cortical activity during REM sleep may provide complementary information, possibly capturing micro-arousals or sleep architecture alterations associated with RBD. Additionally, the low median weights assigned to EOG data indicate that eye movement patterns provide limited predictive power for RBD classification within this framework, a finding that is consistent with clinical understanding.

C. Temporal Importance Analysis

Fig. 7 illustrates a chin EMG signal during a REM episode, the corresponding RAI atonia map, and the temporal importance weights produced by the proposed model trained solely on Chin EMG data. By inspecting the plots, it is revealed a clear alignment between periods marked by the RAI as loss of atonia (black segments in the binary map) and intervals assigned with higher importance by the model (yellow to bright red regions in the lower panel). In particular, clusters of high weights consistently coincide with bursts of

Fig. 4. Distribution of channel attention weights for the independent multi-channel EMG configuration. Boxplots show weights across all patients and stratified by RBD label.

Fig. 5. Distribution of channel attention weights when all EMG, EEG, and EOG signals embeddings are extracted independently. Boxplots show weights across all patients and stratified by RBD label.

Fig. 6. Distribution of channel attention weights when EMG, EEG, and EOG signals are grouped prior to embedding extraction. Boxplots show weights across all patients and stratified by RBD label.

Fig. 7. Temporal analysis of REM episode chin EMG signal. Top: raw chin EMG signal. Middle: binary REM Atonia Index (RAI) map, where dark segments indicate loss of atonia. Bottom: temporal importance weights obtained from LogSumExp pooling.

increased EMG amplitude and with RAI-indicated tonic or phasic muscle activity, suggesting that the model is focusing on physiologically meaningful events associated with REM sleep without atonia.

Furthermore, while the RAI provides a binary characterization of each mini-epoch (atonia or loss of atonia), the model yields a continuous spectrum of temporal importance values. This gradual representation appears to reflect the relative saliency of each time segment, rather than enforcing a strict decision. As a result, transitions are captured more smoothly, and mild levels of muscular activation receive proportional weighting. This behavior allows the model to assign some importance to these regions, hence preserving potentially relevant information that might otherwise be discarded.

V. CONCLUSION

This study presents a DL framework for automated RBD prediction from PSG recordings during REM sleep. By combining the pretrained SleepFM foundation model with a hierarchical classification head, the proposed approach produces RBD probabilities for a given patient while enabling intrinsic relevance weights through attention-based channel pooling and LogSumExp temporal pooling.

Compared with the RAI baseline under identical chin EMG input, the proposed method achieved improved classification balance, notably increasing recall while maintaining competitive precision and AUC. Extending the input to multiple

EMG channels processed independently yielded the highest overall discriminative performance, indicating that limb EMG provides complementary information beyond chin EMG alone. In contrast, grouping channels prior to embedding extraction reduced performance, and adding EEG and EOG signals did not improve results in the present cohort. Attention weights reinforced the primary relevance of muscle activity for RBD characterization, and temporal importance scores aligned with physiologically relevant loss-of-atonia segments while offering a continuous representation of saliency.

Although limited by the small dataset, the results support the potential of DL systems to assist clinicians in efficiently and reliably detecting RBD from PSG signals. Future lines of work include the comparison of other RBD detection methods against SOMNUS-RBD, the exploration of other data modalities (e.g. synchronized video), as well as finetuning of the SleepFM foundation model.

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